

RADIO HEALTH COMMUNICATION AND ADOPTION OF LASSA FEVER PREVENTIVE MEASURES AMONG MARKET WOMEN IN JALINGO, TARABA STATE, NIGERIA

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DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20629536>

Abstract

Lassa fever remains a persistent public health challenge in Nigeria, with Taraba State identified as one of the high-burden areas despite media intervention efforts. This study examined exposure to radio-based Lassa fever prevention messages, knowledge regarding preventive measures, and the adoption of preventive practices among market women in Jalingo, Taraba State, Nigeria. The study was framed on Protection Motivation Theory (PMT) and applied a qualitative research design using in-depth interviews with 18 purposively selected market women across major markets in Jalingo metropolis. Data were collected using a semi-structured interview guide, and analysed using deductive thematic analysis. Findings reveal limited and inconsistent exposure to radio-based Lassa fever prevention messages, which were largely restricted to occasional jingles and brief awareness segments. Participants demonstrated basic awareness of rodent control as a preventive measure; however, knowledge of broader preventive practices such as food hygiene, environmental sanitation, and early symptom recognition remained inadequate and weakly linked to radio communication exposure. Furthermore, adoption of preventive measures was poor and inconsistent, with respondents reporting reliance on personal experience and informal social networks rather than media messaging. The study concludes that radio-based health communication in its current form is insufficient to generate comprehensive knowledge and sustained behavioural change among market women. The findings underscore the need for integrated risk communication strategies that combine enhanced radio programming with community-based health education and infrastructural improvements to support effective Lassa fever prevention in high-risk settings.

Introduction

Lassa fever remains a persistent and significant public health threat in Nigeria and other parts of West Africa, with recurring outbreaks and substantial mortality (Eneh et al. 2025). It is an acute viral haemorrhagic disease caused by the Lassa virus, transmitted primarily through contact with food or household items contaminated by urine or faeces of infected multimammate rats

(*Mastomys natalensis*), while secondary transmission occurs through direct human-to-human contact, especially in healthcare settings (WHO, 2024). Nigeria bears a disproportionate burden of the disease, with an estimated 100,000–300,000 infections and thousands of deaths annually in West Africa (Africa CDC, n.d; WHO, 2025; Ogundele et al., 2025). The disease is further worsened by delayed diagnosis, weak surveillance systems, limited access to diagnostic facilities, and the absence of a widely available vaccine, making prevention heavily reliant on behavioural and environmental control measures. Consequently, Lassa fever continues to impose a dual burden of biomedical risk and health communication failure in endemic communities.

Existing studies consistently emphasise that risk communication plays a critical role in shaping public knowledge and preventive behaviour in Lassa fever control (Ben-Enukora et al., 2022; Madu et al., 2025). Evidence indicates that radio continues to be one of the most dominant and trusted mass media channels for information dissemination in Nigeria because of its affordability, extensive geographic coverage, and accessibility among low-literacy populations. However, while trust in radio for general news is common, it is not considered as a primary or preferred source for information on Lassa fever. This underscores the insufficiency of instructional content in existing radio programmes and reinforces the need for more targeted, health-specific educational content (Ben-Enukora et al., 2021; Isokpehi et al., 2025). Studies further show that exposure to health communication via radio is associated with improved awareness and knowledge of transmission routes and preventive practices among general populations in endemic states (Talabi & Oko-Epelle, 2024; Ben-Enukora et al., 2021). However, a critical gap remains in the literature regarding how such radio-based health messages translate into knowledge acquisition and actual behavioural adoption among high-risk informal sector populations. In particular, market women who operate in environments highly exposed to rodent infestation due to poor sanitation and food handling conditions have been underrepresented in empirical research. There is limited context-specific evidence from urban markets examining the exposure to radio messages on Lassa fever prevention, the knowledge derived from such exposure, and how this knowledge influences preventive behaviour among women in urban markets. Addressing this gap is important because markets represent key nodes of daily human interaction where disease transmission risks are amplified, and behavioural change among traders majorly women can significantly influence community-level disease control outcomes.

Against this backdrop, this study investigates the exposure of market women in Jalingo to radio-based information on Lassa fever protection measures, assesses their level of knowledge regarding the disease, and examines how such knowledge influences the adoption of preventive practices. By focusing on radio as a primary communication channel and market women as a vulnerable but influential population group, the study contributes to understanding the communication–behaviour nexus in infectious disease prevention.

Statement of the Problem

Taraba State ranks among the leading states with confirmed Lassa fever cases and deaths in Nigeria. The NCDC situation report for 2025 revealed that Taraba State recorded 34 deaths out of the 138 Lassa fever deaths documented nationwide between January and May 2025, making it the state with the highest mortality figure during the period (*Guardian News*, 2025; *The Whistler*, 2025). The recurrent outbreaks have been linked to poor environmental sanitation, rodent infestation, inadequate food storage practices, and low adherence to preventive health behaviours, particularly in densely populated commercial environments such as markets where exposure risks

are high. Consequently, market women, who constitute a major segment of daily market users and food handlers, remain highly vulnerable to the transmission of the disease.

In response to the persistent outbreaks, local radio stations in Taraba State such as TSBS, Rock FM, Shimo FM have continued to air sensitization programmes, public health discussions, and awareness jingles aimed at educating residents on Lassa fever transmission pathways and motivating the adoption of preventive measures such as proper hygiene, environmental sanitation, safe food storage, and rodent control. These radio campaigns are particularly important because radio remains one of the most accessible and influential media platforms in semi-urban and rural communities due to its affordability, language flexibility, and wide audience reach. However, despite the sustained dissemination of Lassa fever awareness messages through radio, the extent to which these campaigns are yielding meaningful outcomes among vulnerable groups such as market women remains unclear. Specifically, there is limited empirical evidence regarding the exposure of market women to radio-based Lassa fever messages, their understanding of the recommended protective measures, and the extent to which such exposure translates into the actual adoption of preventive behaviours. It is against this backdrop that the current study investigates radio health communication and the adoption of Lassa fever protective measures among market women in Jalingo metropolis, Taraba State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

This specific objectives of the study are:

1. Explore the exposure of market women in major markets in Jalingo metropolis, Taraba State, to radio information on Lassa fever preventive measures.
2. Examine the knowledge and understanding of Lassa fever preventive measures among market women in Jalingo metropolis based on exposure to radio health campaign messages.
3. Investigate the adoption of Lassa fever preventive measures communicated through radio campaigns among market women in Jalingo metropolis.

Review of Empirical Studies

Empirical scholarship on Lassa fever in Nigeria has largely concentrated on assessing levels of awareness, knowledge, attitudes, and preventive practices among different population groups, with most studies adopting quantitative cross-sectional approaches. For example, Ossai (2020) investigated knowledge and preventive measures against Lassa fever among household heads in Abakaliki metropolis using a descriptive survey design and reported high levels of awareness and positive preventive practices among respondents. Similarly, Areji et al. (2023), in their study among women in Nnewi North Local Government Area of Anambra State, found that respondents demonstrated good knowledge, positive attitudes, and substantial compliance with preventive measures. While these studies contribute important epidemiological and behavioural insights, their reliance on structured questionnaires and descriptive statistical analysis limits deeper understanding of how individuals interpret, negotiate, and internalize prevention messages within their socio-cultural realities. More importantly, the studies largely present awareness and preventive practices as linear outcomes without critically interrogating the communication processes and contextual factors shaping such behaviours.

A major trend observable in the literature is the growing recognition of media, particularly radio, as a critical platform for disseminating Lassa fever information in endemic communities. Ben-Enukora et al. (2020), through Focus Group Discussions on indigenous Yoruba-language radio jingles in Ondo State, demonstrated that radio campaigns enhanced awareness of Lassa fever among women. However, the study also revealed a contradiction between awareness and behavioural compliance, as many respondents still exhibited poor attitudes toward rodents and failed to consistently adopt recommended preventive practices. This finding challenges assumptions in earlier quantitative studies that exposure to health information automatically translates into behavioural change. Similarly, Adesoji et al. (2016) found that although respondents in Ilorin had received information about Lassa fever through radio, television, newspapers, and social media, misconceptions regarding transmission and prevention remained widespread. Aromolaran et al. (2023) equally reported that despite high awareness levels among residents in Osun State, only a small proportion possessed adequate knowledge of the disease. Collectively, these studies suggest that media exposure alone may not be sufficient to produce meaningful behavioural outcomes, thereby indicating the need for more context-sensitive investigations into how audiences interpret and utilize health messages communicated through radio campaigns.

Another significant limitation in existing literature is the inadequate scholarly attention given to market women as a high-risk and communication-sensitive population. Although Adegoke et al. (2017) examined foodstuff sellers' knowledge and preventive practices regarding Lassa fever in Ibadan markets, the study focused primarily on sanitation and rodent control practices without critically exploring the role of health communication in shaping such behaviours. Furthermore, while the qualitative approach adopted by the study provided useful contextual insights, it did not specifically interrogate the influence of radio-based sensitization campaigns on preventive action. Likewise, studies such as Ighedosa et al. (2016), which assessed students' knowledge and preventive practices in the University of Benin, concentrated on institutional populations that differ considerably from informal market populations in terms of media access, literacy levels, and exposure conditions.

It can be deduced from prior literature so far that, there remains limited empirical understanding of how market women who operate in environments characterized by poor sanitation, rodent infestation, and high human interaction engage with radio health messages on Lassa fever prevention. In addition, most existing studies are geographically concentrated in southwestern and southeastern Nigeria, with limited evidence from highly affected northern states such as Taraba State where recurrent outbreaks continue to occur. Therefore, the current study departs from previous descriptive and predominantly quantitative studies by qualitatively examining radio health communication and the adoption of Lassa fever protective measures among market women in Jalingo metropolis, Taraba State. By focusing on the lived experiences, interpretations, and behavioural responses of market women to radio sensitization campaigns, the study seeks to provide deeper insight into the communication-behaviour relationship in the context of infectious disease prevention.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Protection Motivation Theory (PMT), propounded by R. W. Rogers in 1975 to explain how individuals respond to perceived health threats and adopt protective behaviours (Balla & Hagger, 2024). The theory emerged from fear appeal research in health communication and posits that individuals are more likely to engage in preventive actions when

they perceive a health threat as severe, consider themselves vulnerable to the threat, believe that recommended preventive measures are effective, and possess confidence in their ability to carry out such measures (Tannenbaum et al., 2015). These components are categorized into two major cognitive appraisal processes: threat appraisal, which involves perceived severity and vulnerability, and coping appraisal, which involves response efficacy and self-efficacy.

The relevance of PMT to the current study lies in its capacity to explain how exposure to radio-based health communication may influence the adoption of Lassa fever protective measures among market women in Jalingo metropolis, Taraba State. Radio sensitization programmes and jingles on stations such as Rock FM, TSBS, and other local broadcasters are designed not only to create awareness about the severity and transmission risks of Lassa fever but also to encourage listeners to adopt preventive practices such as proper hygiene, safe food storage, environmental sanitation, and rodent control. From the perspective of PMT, market women are more likely to adopt these preventive measures if radio messages successfully communicate the seriousness of Lassa fever, increase their perception of personal susceptibility, and convince them that the recommended measures are both effective and practicable within their market environments.

Research Methodology

This study adopted a qualitative research design using in-depth interviews. The qualitative approach was considered appropriate because the study sought to obtain detailed insights into participants' experiences, perceptions, interpretations, and behavioural responses to radio sensitization messages on Lassa fever prevention. The study population comprised market women drawn from major markets within Jalingo metropolis, where commercial activities, food handling practices, and environmental sanitation conditions increase vulnerability to rodent infestation and possible exposure to Lassa fever transmission.

The study employed purposive sampling to select participants considered information-rich and relevant to the objectives of the study. Purposive sampling was appropriate because it enabled the researcher to deliberately select market women who were actively involved in trading activities and had exposure to local radio stations such as Rock FM, TSBS, and other stations. This approach ensured that participants possessed adequate contextual experience to provide meaningful insights into their exposure to radio health messages, understanding of Lassa fever preventive measures, and behavioural responses to such messages.

Data collection was achieved through saturation principle. Saturation was reached after interviewing 18 respondents, which constituted the final sample size for the study. Data were collected through using a semi-structured interview guide. The interview were conducted in Local Language particularly Hausa. All interviews were translated, transcribed and analysed using Deductive thematic analysis with themes derived according to the objectives of the study. This approach of analysis resonates with current study because coding is guided by predefined concepts, hence, improves analytical transparency and replicability, particularly in policy-relevant health studies where clarity is essential (Nowell et al., 2017).

Data Presentation

Profile of the Participants

Market Location	No. Participants	Code	Trade Categories	Average Years in Business
Jalingo Main Market	5	PT 1-5	Foodstuff/Grains	6-9 years
Nukkai Market	5	PT 6-10	Vegetables/Provisions	5-10 years
Mayo-Gwoi Market	4	PT 11-14	Perishable Food Items	5-15 years
Mile 6 Market	4	PT 15-18	Fish/Rice/Spices	2-7 years
Total	18			

Theme 1: Exposure to Lassa Fever Prevention Measures through Radio

Based on the interview responses, the major theme identified in relation to the first research question is that market women in Jalingo have occasional exposure to information on Lassa fever through radio, particularly through jingles and a few discussion programmes. However, the respondents indicated that such information is not frequent or detailed enough to provide adequate knowledge on prevention measures. Most participants noted that they only hear about Lassa fever during outbreak periods, after which radio messages on the disease become scarce. According to Participant 1, “I hear about Lassa fever sometimes on radio, especially the jingles they play, but it is not always” (PT1).

Similarly, Participant 7 stated that:

There are times radio stations in Jalingo discuss Lassa fever on radio programmes, mostly when there is an outbreak, but after some time, we stop hearing about it again. I think the report about Lassa fever is only high on radio when there is report of casualties from the Federal medical Center Jalingo [...] (PT 7).

In the same vein, Participant 11 noted:

I know about Lassa fever through radio announcements, but the information is not regular enough for people in the market to really learn how to prevent it properly. I believed that the sensitization awareness against Lassa fever prevention is generally low in the state despite the increasing cases of the disease in recent time [...] (PT 11).

The responses above suggest that although radio serves as a source of awareness on Lassa fever prevention among market women in Jalingo, Taraba State, there is limited exposure to comprehensive prevention messages.

Theme 2: Knowledge of Lassa Fever Prevention Measures

The interviews revealed that market women in Jalingo, Taraba State possess some knowledge regarding Lassa fever prevention measures. Most participants demonstrated awareness that rats are the major carriers of the disease and emphasized the need to maintain a rodent-free environment. However, their understanding of other preventive measures, such as proper food storage, environmental sanitation, personal hygiene, and early medical intervention, appeared limited. The findings also indicate that their knowledge was largely not connected to radio

campaign messages, as many respondents stated that they could not recall learning about Lassa fever prevention through radio programmes.

According to Participant 6:

What I know about Lassa fever is that it comes from rats and dirty environments where rats stay. People usually say we should avoid rats touching our food, but apart from that, I don't really know other preventive measures very well. I cannot say that I learnt these things from radio because I hardly hear detailed programmes about Lassa fever prevention on radio stations (PT6)

Similarly, Participant 7 stated:

The only thing I have always heard is that rats spread Lassa fever, and because of that we try to keep food away from rats. But I don't really know if there are other important ways people can protect themselves or what someone should do when symptoms start showing.

In the same vein, Participant 8 explained:

I know that Lassa fever is dangerous and that people can get it from rats, but I am not sure about all the ways to prevent it completely. Maybe washing hands regularly, covering food properly, and keeping the environment clean can help, but I am not certain. Honestly, I cannot remember learning anything serious about Lassa fever prevention from radio (PT 8).

Additionally, Participant 18 asserted:

I have heard several times that rats are responsible for spreading Lassa fever, but I do not know what somebody is expected to do when a person becomes infected or how families can fully protect themselves from the disease. Sometimes I listen to radio programmes once in a while, but I cannot clearly remember hearing any detailed programme or discussion that taught me about Lassa fever prevention measures (PT18).

The responses suggest that although the participants possess basic awareness about the relationship between rats and Lassa fever, their overall knowledge of comprehensive prevention measures remains inadequate. The findings further indicate that radio campaigns have not significantly contributed to improving detailed knowledge of Lassa fever prevention among the market women.

Theme 3: Adoption of Lassa Fever Prevention Measures

The study further revealed poor adoption of Lassa fever prevention measures among the market women. Although a few participants reported taking certain preventive actions, such as using rat traps, rat poison, and regular cleaning of their shops and homes, the majority emphasized that these practices were not influenced by radio campaign messages. Instead, they explained that their actions were largely motivated by personal experience, advice from family members, and general environmental concerns. The findings also showed that many participants faced difficulties maintaining effective preventive practices because of the nature of the market environment, poor sanitation systems, and inadequate waste disposal facilities.

According to Participant 12:

I always try my best to control rats by using traps and sometimes chemicals both in my shop and at home, but the problem is that the rats still come back after some time. In a market where food items are everywhere, it is very difficult to completely stop rats from moving around. The truth is that the little effort I make is not because of any radio programme, but mainly because my children and other family members always advise me to be careful about rats and dirty surroundings (PT 12).

Similarly, Participant 15 stated:

I sweep and clean my shop every day because I do not like dirty environments, especially where food is being sold. But honestly, I cannot say that I do these things because I heard any serious radio campaign about Lassa fever prevention. Most times, I am too busy in the market to listen to radio programmes, and even when I listen occasionally, I hardly hear detailed discussions that can really influence my behaviour.”

In the same vein, Participant 14 explained:

At home and sometimes in the shop and at home, we use rat poison and traps to reduce rats, but despite all those efforts, rats still appear from time to time because the market is large and many people sell food items openly. What we really need in this market are proper waste disposal containers and better sanitation support from authorities, not only radio programmes that many traders do not even have enough time to listen to regularly (PT 14).

The responses indicate that the adoption of Lassa fever prevention measures among the market women remains limited and inconsistent. While some preventive actions are practiced, they are mainly driven by personal initiative and social influence rather than exposure to radio campaigns. The findings further suggest that environmental and infrastructural challenges significantly hinder effective adherence to Lassa fever prevention measures.

Discussion of Findings

The primary objective of this study was to assess exposure to Lassa fever prevention information via radio among market women in Jalingo, Taraba State. Findings from the interviews indicate that participants have limited and inconsistent exposure to such information. Although some women reported occasional awareness of Lassa fever through radio, particularly via jingles or brief public health discussions, the exposure was largely episodic and insufficient to support sustained health knowledge. This finding is consistent with Aromolaran et al. (2023), who observed that although awareness of Lassa fever may be relatively high in some populations, depth of knowledge regarding prevention remains limited due to inadequate and irregular health communication exposure.

The study further examined the knowledge of Lassa fever prevention measures among the participants. Findings show that while respondents demonstrated basic awareness of rodent control as a preventive measure, their understanding of broader preventive practices such as safe food handling, personal hygiene, environmental sanitation, and early symptom recognition was limited. Importantly, this knowledge was not strongly linked to radio-based health communication, suggesting weak media influence on health literacy in this context. Similar evidence was reported by Adesoji et al. (2016), who found that exposure to Lassa fever information does not necessarily translate into accurate or comprehensive knowledge, as misconceptions often persist even among

informed populations. Conversely, Areji et al. (2023) reported higher levels of comprehensive knowledge among women in Nnewi North LGA, indicating that effective health education interventions can significantly enhance understanding of multiple prevention strategies. The observed variation may reflect differences in the intensity, consistency, and targeting of public health messaging across regions.

From theoretical framework perspective (PMT), this pattern suggests a gap in both coping appraisal and response efficacy. While individuals may recognise Lassa fever as a health threat, limited understanding of diverse preventive measures may weaken their perception of the effectiveness of available protective actions, thereby constraining behavioural motivation (Maddux & Rogers, 1983). In practical terms, this implies that awareness without adequate instructional content is insufficient to drive meaningful preventive behaviour among the target population.

In addition, the study assessed the adoption of Lassa fever prevention measures among the participants. Findings indicate generally poor and inconsistent adherence to recommended preventive practices. Although some respondents reported using rodent traps and chemicals, these measures were largely ineffective in eliminating rodent infestation due to persistent environmental conditions characteristic of market settings. Participants also reported inadequate waste management practices, attributing this to time constraints and the absence of designated waste disposal infrastructure within the market environment. These findings corroborate Ighedosa et al. (2016), who reported inconsistent preventive behaviours despite awareness of Lassa fever among university students, and Adegoke et al. (2017), who similarly found that structural constraints, economic limitations, and environmental conditions hinder full compliance with rodent control practices among food vendors. The results generally suggests that effective Lassa fever prevention requires not only individual knowledge and awareness but also supportive environmental and infrastructural systems that enable sustained behavioural adoption.

Conclusion

This study examined exposure, knowledge, and adoption of Lassa fever prevention measures among market women in Jalingo, Taraba State, with particular attention to radio as an information channel. The findings reveal persistent gaps in access to and utilisation of radio-based health communication on Lassa fever prevention. Although radio campaigns exist within the study context, exposure among participants was limited and largely restricted to general awareness messages, with insufficient depth to support comprehensive understanding of preventive practices beyond basic rodent control. The study further demonstrates that knowledge of Lassa fever prevention among the respondents remains poor. In addition, adoption of preventive practices was inconsistent, as efforts such as rodent control were constrained by persistent environmental conditions, particularly inadequate waste disposal systems and the structural realities of market settings. These findings are, however, interpreted within certain methodological limitations. The study is limited by its qualitative design and relatively small sample size, which restricts the generalisability of the findings beyond the selected markets in Jalingo metropolis.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. State health authorities and broadcast stations should redesign Lassa fever prevention messages to move beyond brief jingles and episodic announcements. Radio content should be structured into regular, segmented educational programmes that clearly explain transmission pathways, comprehensive prevention measures, and appropriate response actions.
2. The Ministry of Health and NCDC should implement periodic, on-site health education campaigns within markets. These interventions should complement radio messaging by providing face-to-face demonstrations on food hygiene, rodent control, waste management, and early symptom recognition.
3. Future health campaign messages on Lassa fever should move beyond fear appeals and instead prioritise practical, actionable guidance. Such messages should be designed to strengthen response efficacy and self-efficacy by equipping market women and other at-risk populations with clear, step-by-step information on prevention and control measures.
4. Health communication strategies should adopt a multi-platform approach combining radio, community outreach, mobile messaging, and interpersonal communication.

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